

ETHOSOMAL GEL: AN ADVANCED APPROACH FOR ENHANCED TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY AND SKIN PENETRATION

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ABSTRACT

Transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) is gaining popularity due to its advantages, which include avoidance of first-pass effect, increased patient compliance, and controlled drug release. Unfortunately, the stratum corneum is one of the barriers of penetration and absorption of several therapeutic agents. Moreover, the stratum corneum reduces the skin permeation of hydrophilic drugs and with high molecular weight. To address this issue, several vesicular carriers, including ethosomes, have been investigated. Ethosomes are phospholipid vesicles contain a large percentage of ethanol. Ethanol facilitates drug passage through the skin by increasing the fluidity of both the vesicular lipid bilayer and the intercellular lipids in the stratum corneum. Thus, the simultaneous presence of ethanol and phospholipids leads to enhanced penetration into the skin, resulting in improved bioavailability and efficacy. Additionally, ethosome gels

prolong the contact of drugs with the skin surface. These gels possess advantages such as convenient application, sustained drug release, and good stability. The present study considered different parameters affecting ethosome preparation, entrapment efficiency, and skin absorption, as well as evaluation techniques for these characteristics. Ethosomal gel systems represents a novel advancement in dermal drug delivery. They represent a novel method for solving problems related to the skin barrier and can be used to deliver numerous drugs.

KEYWORDS: Ethosomes, Transdermal drug delivery, Skin permeation, Phospholipids, Controlled release, Topical delivery.

INTRODUCTION

The skin is one of the largest and most accessible organs in the body, and using it to administer medication has many benefits over conventional drug delivery methods. Except for lipophilic and low molecular weight drugs. The stratum corneum is the most powerful barrier to the passage of most medications, making the skin an excellent barrier to molecular transport. This method is called transdermal drug delivery, which uses a person's skin as a route for a drug molecule to enter the body and be delivered systemically.^[1]

The transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) is a controlled drug delivery system in which the primary objective is to administer medication through the skin at a predetermined and precisely regulated rate. The transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) offers considerably greater advantages, especially regarding drugs that demonstrate significantly poor permeation across the stratum corneum layer of skin.^[2]

Transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS) offer several advantages over oral drug delivery, including bypassing the first pass effect and gastrointestinal tract irritation. Nevertheless, the primary disadvantage of this approach is the barrier action of the stratum corneum, as only lipophilic drugs with a molecular weight of less than 500 g/mol can permeate the skin. Transdermal drug delivery systems have many benefits, including avoidance of first-pass effect on the liver, drug delivery control, reduced dose frequency, and better patient compliance. This is due to the fact that transdermal drug delivery is minimally invasive and convenient for patients. The most obvious drawback of transdermal drug delivery includes the low permeability of the skin.^[3]

Numerous technological developments have occurred in recent decades to address skin barrier issue. These methods include physical techniques such as iontophoresis, sonophoresis and microneedles, as well as chemical methods that utilize penetration enhancers and biochemical approaches, involving liposomal vesicles and enzyme inhibitors. Methods such as iontophoresis, microneedles, and sonophoresis are complex to implement and may affect patient adherence. The application of chemical enhancers, such as surfactants and organic solvents leads to irritation, harm, and decreased skin barrier function; thus, it is preferable to administer therapeutic agents that preserve normal skin barrier function without relying on a chemical enhancer. One method involves utilizing vesicular systems.^[4]

Lipid and surfactant vesicular carriers have been extensively studied because of their potential to promote drug passage through the skin. The vesicles can interact with the lipid layers of the stratum corneum, enabling drug diffusion into the skin and permitting the inclusion of diverse drugs, including hydrophobic and hydrophilic compounds. Due to the intrinsic barrier function of the skin, conventional dosage forms are restricted in terms of penetration depth; hence, there is a need for innovative approaches to increase skin permeability.^[5]

Liposomes and niosomes are the two most frequently investigated vesicular carriers used for dermal drug administration. Despite their potential benefits, their application is limited by factors such as instability and inability to penetrate deeply into the skin. Although these vehicles have an ability to entrapped drug molecules in the epidermis, they are incapable of providing adequate systemic drug delivery.^[6]

To resolve these problems, more advanced deformable vesicles such as transfersomes and ethosomes are under investigation. With these vesicles, it is possible to increase the penetration of drugs into the stratum corneum by utilizing certain materials, including surfactants and a high amount of alcohol. Out of these, ethosomes have been receiving considerable attention due to their efficiency in increasing the penetration of drugs.^[7]

Touitou *et al.* developed ethosomes in 1997.^[8] These structures have emerged as an innovative drug delivery mechanism, providing substantial improvements in both transdermal and topical uses. These vesicular transporters, made of phospholipids, ethanol, and water, facilitate the administration of both hydrophilic and lipophilic medications through the skin. Through increased permeability and stability, ethosomes address the shortcomings of

traditional delivery systems, proving especially effective for skin disorders, fungal infections, and systemic diseases.^[9] These flexible, soft vesicles are designed to enhance the spread of active compounds in the skin. Given the elevated levels of ethanol and lipid concentrations in ethosomes, understanding their effect on the skin is crucial. The ethanol content of the formulation has been noted to boost drug solubility and promote the creation of lipid structures that can flexibly navigate between skin corneocytes, thereby enhancing medication absorption and retention within the skin.^{[10],[11]} Ethosomes are vesicles that vary in size from approximately 30 nm to several micrometers. Reports suggest that when prepared using the same approach without a size-reduction phase, ethosomes tend to be smaller than liposomes. The decrease in size is linked to the high ethanol levels, as vesicle size diminishes with rising ethanol concentrations between about 20-45%.^[12]

The zeta potential of ethosomes, a measure of surface charge, significantly influences their interaction with the skin. While a high negative charge might typically suggest electrostatic repulsion, the dynamic nature of the skin's lipid environment and the ethosomes ability to deform can facilitate their penetration despite this charge.^[13]

The high concentration of ethanol in ethosomes enhances their flexibility and deformability, allowing them to squeeze through the intercellular spaces of the stratum corneum, the outermost layer of the skin. This flexibility is crucial for overcoming the skin barrier without causing drug leakage during the process.^[14]

Figure 1: Structure of Ethosomes.

ADVANTAGES OF ETHOSOMES

1. The use of ethanol increases the permeability of drugs through corneocytes in the skin due to its effect on lipid fluidity and flexibility of vesicles.
2. The delivery system allows a drug to dissolve both in a lipid and water phases, thus promoting microcirculation in the skin as well as entry into the bloodstream.
3. Ethosomes allow delivery of hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds as well as peptides and proteins.
4. The composition of ethosomes is recognized as safe, non-toxic and has been approved in pharmaceutical, biotechnological, veterinary, cosmetic and nutritional applications.
5. Its delivery mechanism is non invasive and ready for rapid commercial application.
6. The delivery method requires high compliance from the patient since it is provided in the form of gel and cream, which is easy to use by patients.
7. Drug delivery using ethosomes is simple and economical compared to iontophoretic and sonophoretic delivery systems.
8. Simple and economical scaling up of industrial manufacture without the use of sophisticated technology required by iontophoresis.
9. The ethosomal system has a high entrapment capacity for both water-soluble and fat-soluble drugs.
10. The delivery system exhibited stability during long-term storage.
11. Alcohol in ethosomes acts as a natural preservative, eliminating the need for additional preservatives.
12. Concentration of a drug does not affect skin delivery of drugs using ethosomes.^{[10], [15]}

DISADVANTAGES OF ETHOSOMES

1. Some individuals may experience allergic reactions to ethanol or other components of the ethosomal formulation.
2. Unlike other carriers, such as polymeric or lipid nanoparticles, which support multiple delivery routes, ethosomes are mainly limited to transdermal application.
3. These systems are better suited for potent drugs that are typically administered in low doses daily.
4. Only drugs with suitable molecular sizes for skin absorption can be efficiently delivered using ethosomes.
5. Certain excipients and penetration enhancers used in ethosomal formulations may cause skin irritation or contact dermatitis in sensitive individuals.^{[10], [15]}

TYPES OF ETHOSOMES

1. Conventional ethosomes (Classic ethosomes)

Ethosome are vesicular delivery systems that consists of phospholipids, high concentrations of ethanol (normally varying from 20% to 45%), and water. Notably the inclusion of ethanol is essential because it enhances the fluidity of the membrane and destabilizes the compact structure of lipids present in the stratum corneum, which in turn increases the permeation properties of drugs across the skin. This vesicular system can carry both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. Being small-sized and flexible, these vesicles are able to pass easily through minute intercellular spaces.^[16]

2. Binary ethosomes

Binary Ethosomes are advanced ethosomes which consist of two types of alcohols. These two alcohols are normally either ethanol and propylene glycol or ethanol and isopropyl alcohol with phospholipids and water. They exhibit increased solubility of the drug because of their composition by addition of another alcohol and stability. This is because of the role played by the two alcohols which is break down the lipid layer of the skin. Thus, these binary ethosomes are ideal for drugs which are poorly soluble.^[17]

3. Transethosomes

The transethosome delivery method is an advanced version of ethosomal vesicles using the mixture of phospholipids, ethanol, and edge activator such as Tween 80, Span 60, or sodium cholate. While the ethanol increases the permeability of the skin by changing its lipid structure, the edge activator increases the flexibility of the membrane of the vesicles. Therefore, the vesicles become able to squeeze themselves into tiny holes in the skin to deliver their content deep into the skin.^[18]

COMPOSITION OF ETHOSOMES

Ethanol

Ethanol is a potent penetration enhancer. It contributes significantly to ethosomal formulations by providing the vesicles with unique features, such as improved skin permeability, stability, zeta potential, entrapment efficacy, and size. According to reports, the ethanol concentrations in ethosomal systems range from 10% to 50%. If the ethanol concentration were raised over the optimal level, the bilayer would become leaky, which would cause the vesicles to become more soluble in ethanol due to a slight increase in size and a large drop in entrapment efficiency.^[19]

Vesicular charge is a significant factor that can affect vesicular characteristics, such as stability and vesicle-skin interaction. The vesicular charge changes from positive to negative due to the increased ethanol content in ethosomes. Because ethanol gives the ethosomal system's surface a negative charge, it keeps the vesicular system from aggregating as a result of electrostatic repulsion. Furthermore, it was discovered that ethanol had stabilising properties. The entrapment efficiency was shown to have a linear relationship with ethanol concentrations between 20% and 40%. Optimising the ethanol concentration throughout the formulation process is crucial because of this. ^{[19],[10]}

Phospholipids

The ethosomal system has been developed using phospholipids from various sources. The selection of phospholipid type and concentration is a crucial step in the formulation of the ethosomal system, as it affects the vesicle's size, stability, zeta potential, entrapment efficacy, and penetrating abilities. ^{[19],[20],[10]}

Phospholipid concentrations in ethosomal formulations typically range from 0.5% to 5%. Vesicular size will slightly or moderately increase with an increase in phospholipid concentration, while entrapment efficiency will increase significantly. This holds true, though, only up to a certain concentration, after which further increases in the concentration of phospholipids will not impact the efficiency of entrapment. This can be explained by the fact that after a certain phospholipid concentration, the vesicles become saturated with the drug. Any additional phospholipids will not be able to entrap more drug, hence the entrapment efficiency plateaus. ^[21] Conversely, larger vesicles were produced by higher phospholipid levels, most likely as a result of the vesicular structural thickening. Thus, the lowest possible vesicle size is achieved when phospholipid concentrations are low and ethanol levels are high. ^[22]

Cholesterol

Since cholesterol is a rigid steroid molecule, adding it to ethosomal systems increases the stability and effectiveness of active ingredient entrapment. In addition to lowering vesicular fusion and permeability, it prevents leaks. Cholesterol reduces the flexibility and permeability of membranes while controlling their fluidity. Ethosomes become more rigid when added to the mixture, so limiting the amount of the active substance that can permeate. On the other hand, because cholesterol has stabilising properties, high cholesterol concentrations improve medication entrapment efficiency. In general, it is used at a concentration of <3%. ^{[20],[10],[22]}

Propylene Glycol (PG)

The penetration enhancer PG is extensively utilised. It has been observed to affect the ethosomal features of size, entrapment efficiency, permeability, and stability when utilised in the production of binary ethosomes at concentrations between 5% and 20%. Particle size will decrease significantly in ethosomal systems when PG is added as compared to non-PG systems. Better drug solubility, higher entrapment efficiency, and improved drug distribution throughout the vesicle are the results of ethanol and PG incorporation in ethosomes.^{[23],[24]}

Edge activators and Penetration enhancers

A crucial step in the formulation of transethosomes is selecting an appropriate edge activator or penetration enhancer, as these components have a significant impact on the properties of the ethosomal system. While preparing transethosomes, a variety of edge activators and penetration enhancers are employed, with tweens and spans being the most often utilised.^{[19],[10],[25]}

SKIN PERMEATION MECHANISM OF ETHOSOMES

Although the precise process of drug delivery in ethosomes has not yet been defined, the increase in drug transport by ethosomes has been attributed to their interaction with skin lipids. The stratum corneum is composed of lipid layers that are closely packed and well-structured at body temperature. There are primarily two mechanisms through which ethosomes achieve efficient drug delivery. One is termed the "ethanol effect". Ethosomes differ from other vesicles because of the high content of ethanol in them. Ethanol is said to affect the structure of the lipid layer of skin; hence, the inclusion of ethanol in the vesicle membrane helps it to pass through the skin's stratum corneum. Moreover, the presence of high amounts of ethanol makes the lipid layer of ethosomes less organized than that of regular vesicles while maintaining their stability, giving them a flexible structure to pass through narrow gaps such as those formed by disruption of stratum corneum's lipid layers.

Figure 2: Mechanism of penetration of ethosomal drug delivery system.

Ethanol Effect: Ethanol enhances the permeation through the skin via a well-defined mechanism: it increases the fluidity of the cell membrane lipids after penetrating the intracellular lipids; and reduces the density of the lipid multi-layered structures in the cell membrane.

Ethosome Effect: It increases the fluidity of the cell membrane lipids with the help of ethanol present in the ethosomes, and hence improves skin permeability.^[26]

METHODS OF PREPARATION OF ETHOSOMES

Hot method

This method requires heating phospholipid in a water bath to 40°C until a colloidal solution is achieved. Propylene glycol and ethanol should be properly mixed in a different container. The aqueous phase receives the organic phase after both mixtures attain 40°C. Subsequently, the drug solution is incorporated, and the phospholipid dispersion is stirred continuously for 10 minutes with a magnetic stirrer operating at 1500 rpm. Finally, the prepared formulations were stored in a refrigerator.^[27]

Cold method

This is the most extensively used and well-liked method for ethosomal preparation. After dissolving the medication and phospholipid in ethanol, it was combined with propylene glycol and heated to 300°C for one hour. Double-distilled water was added and constantly swirled for five minutes to create the final dispersion. An ethosomal formulation's vesicle size can be decreased to the required level by sonication or extrusion. Lastly, keep the mixture chilled.^[28]

Classic Mechanical Dispersion Method

Soy phosphatidylcholine is dissolved in the presence of chloroform and ethanol in a ratio of 3:1 in a round bottom flask. Evaporation of the organic solvents takes place using a vacuum rotary evaporator at temperatures higher than the lipid transition temperatures, resulting in formation of a lipid film within the flask. Lastly, through vacuuming of the contents for an entire night, all traces of the organic solvents are eliminated in the lipid film. Hydration is done through rotation of the flask at the right temperature using varying amounts of a hydroethanolic solution with the drug.^[29]

CHARACTERIZATION OF ETHOSOMAL GELS

Vesicle Size and Polydispersity Index (PDI)

Particle size is one of the most critical parameters determining the skin penetration ability and stability of ethosomes. It is typically measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS) using a zeta sizer. The PDI reflects the homogeneity of the vesicle population; a PDI below 0.3 indicates a monodisperse and uniform preparation. Optimal ethosomal formulations for transdermal delivery typically exhibit vesicle sizes in the range of 100–500 nm.^[30]

Zeta Potential

Zeta potential measures the surface charge of the vesicles and is an indicator of physical stability. Ethosomes generally exhibit a negative zeta potential due to the presence of ethanol and the phospholipid head groups. A zeta potential more negative than –30 mV is considered indicative of a stable formulation, as it prevents vesicular aggregation through electrostatic repulsion.^[31]

Entrapment Efficiency (EE%)

Entrapment efficiency is the percentage of drug incorporated within the ethosomal vesicles relative to the total drug added. It is commonly determined by ultracentrifugation or

ultrafiltration, followed by quantification of the free drug in the supernatant or filtrate by HPLC or UV spectrophotometry. High entrapment efficiency (>70%) is desirable for effective drug loading. Ethosomal formulations generally exhibit superior EE% compared to liposomes due to the ability of ethanol to enhance drug solubility within the lipid bilayer.^[32]

***In vitro* drug permeation study**

The modified Franz diffusion cell equipped with an egg membrane is utilized for conducting *in vitro* permeation studies. These studies are carried out using phosphate buffer saline at a pH of 7.4. The formulation is positioned on the upper side of the membrane within the donor compartment. The temperature is kept constant at $37\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. Samples are collected hourly from the receptor media through a sampling tube, and an equal volume of fresh media is added simultaneously to maintain sink conditions. The collected samples are then analysed using a UV/Vis spectrophotometer model.^[33]

Stability study

The variation in drug entrapment efficiency is used to evaluate the stability of ethosomal vesicles. This is done by storing the vesicles at $40\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75\pm 5\%$ RH for a period of 6 months. At regular intervals during this duration, samples are taken and analysed for changes in pH, colour, drug content, and *in vitro* drug release^[34]

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and FTIR

The DSC technique is employed to investigate the thermal properties of the drug along with excipients present in the ethosomal formulation to validate that no drug-excipient incompatibility exists. The FTIR analysis is performed to determine the functional groups and confirm the entrapment efficiency of the drug into the phospholipid bilayer.^[35]

Physicochemical Characterization of the Gel

Pharmaceutical gels containing ethosomes are characterized based on their pH levels using a digital pH meter (acceptable pH 5.5-7.0); their viscosity using a Brookfield rheometer; their spreadability using spreadability instrument by measuring the force required to spread out the gel; extrudability (force resistance to extrude from the tube); drug homogeneity; and stability at varying conditions such as $2-8^\circ\text{C}$, $25^\circ\text{C}/60\%$ RH, and $40^\circ\text{C}/75\%$ RH according to ICH standards.^[36]

APPLICATION OF ETHOSOMAL FORMULATION

Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic Applications

Ethosomal gels containing NSAIDs like diclofenac, aceclofenac, ketoprofen, and piroxicam have been developed and found effective for treatment of musculoskeletal pain, osteoarthritis, and sports-related injuries via topical administration. Therapeutic levels of drugs are delivered locally at target site without producing any systemic toxicity like that produced by oral NSAID formulations. The permeability of ethosomal gels containing diclofenac was three to fourfold higher than that of normal gels.^[37]

Pilosebaceous Targeting

The pilosebaceous unit plays a vital role in drug delivery through the skin. It serves as a good vehicle for delivering drug treatments for localizing acne, alopecia, and other disorders. Moreover, it may serve as an alternate site for systemic drug delivery. In one study, Maiden *et al.* employed an ethosomal formulation loaded with minoxidil, which is a drug known to be lipophilic and is used in the treatment of hair loss. Experiments performed using nude mice indicated that ethosomal minoxidil produced 2.0, 7.0, and 5.0-fold greater concentrations than ethanolic phospholipid dispersion, hydroethanolic solution, and ethanolic minoxidil, respectively (0.5% drug concentration).^[38]

Antiviral Applications

Acyclovir, used in the management of herpes simplex and herpes zoster infections, has poor bioavailability via the oral route and limited skin penetration in conventional topical formulations. Acyclovir-loaded ethosomal gels demonstrated significantly enhanced skin permeation and antiviral efficacy compared to marketed cream formulations, with better patient acceptability.^[39]

Antifungal Applications

Superficial fungal infections like tinea pedis, tinea corporis, and candidiasis account for a large part of the health burden worldwide. Ethosomes of ketoconazole, fluconazole, and clotrimazole gels show greater efficacy than traditional topical agents for their significant antifungal properties. The increased permeation of the drug into the stratum corneum by using ethosomes will enable the delivery of the antifungal drug to the site of action, usually located in the viable epidermis or upper dermis.^[40]

Delivery of anti-parkinsonism agent

In the year 2000, Dayan and Touitou created an ethosomal formulation of trihexyphenidyl hydrochloride (THP), a psychoactive medication used in the treatment of Parkinson's disease. They compared this formulation with a standard liposomal one. THP functions as an inhibitor of the M1 muscarinic receptor and has a short duration of action, approximately three hours. Because of the motor difficulties associated with Parkinson's disease, it is challenging to administer THP orally. Using electron microscopy, the researchers observed that ethosomes are small phospholipid-based vesicles. The study found that delivering THP through ethosomes significantly improved its penetration through the skin of nude mice. Specifically, the rate of THP transport was 87 times greater than with liposomes, 51 times more than with phosphate buffer, and 4.5 times higher than with a hydroethanolic solution. Furthermore, after 18 hours, the amount of THP retained in the skin was greatest when using ethosomes. These findings suggest that ethosomal delivery systems could be a valuable method for transdermal administration of THP in the management of Parkinson's disease.^[41]

Delivery of problematic drug molecules

Large biogenic compounds such as insulin are challenging to administer orally because the gastrointestinal tract completely breaks them down. Therefore, encapsulating high molecular weight drugs within ethosomes significantly improves their permeability and therapeutic effectiveness.^[39]

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Future research in ethosomal drug delivery is directed toward several promising areas. Functionalized ethosomes modified with ligands, antibodies, or stimuli-responsive polymers represent the next generation of targeted vesicular carriers. pH-sensitive, temperature-sensitive, and redox-responsive ethosomal systems are under investigation for site-specific release in tumor microenvironments and inflammatory tissues.^[42]

The incorporation of microfluidics technology into continuous flow processes is expected to enhance consistency and scalability in manufacturing for commercial purposes. Studies are underway on nano-ethosomes with particle size less than 100 nm for better cell permeability and deeper skin penetration. The use of ethosomes together with physical techniques like microneedles and sonophoresis at low frequency is predicted to optimize the delivery of macromolecules through the skin.^[43]

Biocompatible and biodegradable polymer-coated or surface-modified ethosomes are being developed to improve stability, prolong circulation, and enable targeted delivery. Additionally, the emerging use of natural phospholipids from sustainable sources and the replacement of synthetic excipients with plant-derived alternatives represent green chemistry advances aligned with environmental sustainability goals.^[44]

CONCLUSION

Ethosomal gels represent a highly promising and versatile platform for transdermal and topical drug delivery. Their unique composition — combining phospholipids, high concentrations of ethanol, and water — enables exceptional flexibility, deep skin penetration, and efficient encapsulation of both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. The incorporation of ethosomal vesicles into gel matrices further enhances their therapeutic utility by providing controlled drug release, prolonged skin contact, and improved patient compliance.

As ongoing research continues to deepen understanding of ethosomal permeation mechanisms and to develop next-generation stimuli-responsive and targeted formulations, ethosomal gels are poised to become a cornerstone of modern transdermal drug delivery systems. Continued interdisciplinary collaboration between pharmaceutical scientists, clinicians, and engineers will be essential to fully realize the clinical and commercial potential of this innovative technology.

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